

NOVEL SINTERED METAL FILTER ELEMENTS: PERFORMANCE EVALUATION IN BIOMASS GASIFICATION CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Filtration is an essential step in biomass gasification processes. In synthesis gas applications, where full removal of gas contaminants is required, the filter unit is typically placed upstream the catalytic reformer in the purpose of shielding the reformer from dust deposits and preventing plugging of the catalytic layer. In state-of-the-art biomass gasification concepts, the raw product gas is cooled down to ca. 500 °C prior to filtration. This results in increased oxygen consumption in the reformer as the gas must be reheated after filtration to reach the targeted reforming temperatures of 850-950 °C. To improve the biomass-to-fuel conversion efficiency of biomass gasification-synthesis plants, the latest R&D efforts in this field have been targeted at operating the filter unit at gasifier outlet temperature (750-850 °C), which would eliminate the intermediate cooling and reheating steps.

Filter elements that are currently available for hot gas filtration at temperatures up to 1000 °C are manufactured from metal alloys, high temperature insulation wool or fine ceramic granules. However, these state-of-the-art filter elements have certain restrictions, such as low ductility, high pressure drop or deficient corrosion resistance. With the aim to generate a metal-based filter material withstanding mechanical loads and corrosive conditions, GKN has developed innovative filter elements out of a modified Iron-Chromium-Aluminium powder (material No. 1.4767 mod.). The focus of this work was on evaluating the performance and corrosion resistance of these novel filters in biomass gasification conditions at temperatures up to 750 °C.

The novel metal filter material was first tested at VTT's laboratory to study its long-term corrosion resistance in the presence of H₂S. No degradation or corrosion was observed in the filter sample after 1000 hours of exposure to high sulphur levels (3000-7000 ppm-vol). Twelve one-meter-long filter elements were then implemented into VTT's pilot-scale dual fluidised-bed gasification test facility and operated in steam gasification conditions at temperatures up to 750 °C. Stable operation was achieved even at high filter temperatures (> 700 °C) and no filter breakages occurred. The full-scale filter elements were exposed to reducing conditions for over 300 hours in total. One of the filter elements was removed after the testing period and inspected at GKN. No material degradation could be detected and the protecting oxide layer was intact.

KEYWORDS

metal filters, biomass gasification, hot gas filtration, corrosion resistance

Long-term corrosion tests in reducing conditions

The novel metal filter material of GKN (modified Iron-Chromium-Aluminium) was first tested in a laboratory set-up to study its long-term corrosion resistance in the presence of H₂S. For this purpose, a filter disc with a diameter of 23 mm was manufactured. The test arrangement is illustrated in Figure 1. The test rig comprised of the filter disc and the holder, the quartz reactor, the surrounding electric ovens and the downstream scrubbing steps to remove H₂S from the outlet gas. The feed gas was mixed from bottle gases.

The 1000-h experiment was conducted at a fixed temperature of 700 °C using simulated gasification gas with 3000-7000 ppm H₂S. The feed gas composition is presented in Table 1. The filter disc was mounted inside the quartz reactor and the gases were fed from top. The face velocity on the filter disc was 0.12-0.17 m/s during the experiment. Photographs of the filter disc before and after the experiment are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Test arrangement in long-term corrosion tests.

Table 1. Feed gas composition.

Compound	CO	CO ₂	H ₂	CH ₄	H ₂ O	H ₂ S	N ₂
vol-%	13.0	13.0	13.0	3.5	13.0	0.3-0.7	44.2

Figure 2. Photographs of the filter disc before (left) and after (right) the 1000-h corrosion test.

After the experiment, the surface and cross-section of the filter disc were studied under a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and further analysed with electron dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). The new filter material showed good corrosion resistance as only minor sulphur enrichment was detected on the surface but no penetration of corrosive species into the bulk material was observed. Figure 3 shows a SEM image of the filter disc surface after 1000 h of exposure to simulated gasification gas.

Figure 3. SEM image of the filter disc surface after 1000 h of exposure to simulated gasification gas.

Filtration experiments in biomass gasification conditions

After long-term corrosion experiments, twelve one-meter-long filter elements of GKN (o.d. 6 cm) were implemented into VTT's pilot-scale dual fluidised-bed (DFB) gasification test facility and operated in steam gasification conditions at temperatures up to 750 °C. The objective was to study the particulate removal efficiency and overall performance of the filter elements in biomass gasification conditions. During the experiments, the full-scale elements were exposed to reducing conditions for over 300 hours. Various woody residues, straw and demolition wood were used as feedstock in the test campaigns.

The 200 kW_{th} dual fluidised-bed (DFB) gasification pilot plant, illustrated in Figure 4, is composed of two interconnected fluidised-bed reactors. Biomass feedstock is converted into gasification gas in a circulating fluidised-bed (CFB) gasifier where a mixture of sand and dolomite act as bed material. Entrained char and bed material are separated from the gas stream in a cyclone and transported to a bubbling fluidised-bed (BFB) oxidiser. The unconverted char is combusted in the oxidiser and the heated bed material is transferred back to the gasifier. The heat required for endothermic gasification reactions in the gasifier is mainly supplied by bed material circulation between the two reactors. Flue gases formed in the oxidiser are cooled down, filtered and vented through the stack.

Upon exiting the gasifier, 'raw' gasification gas is directed to the filter unit. The filter unit (i.d. 600 mm, total height 3.6 m) contains 12 candle-type filter elements that are divided into four clusters. The accumulated dust is removed from the filter surface by periodic reverse pulsing with nitrogen. The four filter clusters are pulse cleaned in sequence with one cluster at a time. Following filtration, the particulate-free gas enters a two-stage catalytic reformer where tars and light hydrocarbons are converted to H₂ and CO.

Figure 4. VTT's 200 kW_{th} dual fluidised-bed (DFB) gasification pilot facility located in Bioruukki, Espoo.

Good filtration performance was achieved with GKN's filter elements during the DFB gasification test campaigns. Stable operation was obtained (stable baseline pressure drop) and no filter breakages occurred during the experiments. An example of the filter pressure drop curve is presented in Figure 5. Particulate samples were retrieved downstream the filter unit to study the particulate removal efficiency. Particulate sampling was carried out isokinetically according to ISO 9096 standard. The particulate concentration in the gas at filter outlet was below the detection limit (< 5 mg/m³n), which indicated that full removal of particulates was achieved.

Figure 5. Stable filter operation in DFB gasification test campaigns with bark as feedstock.

One of the filter elements (Figure 6) was retrieved from the DFB pilot and analysed at GKN after being exposed to biomass gasification conditions for over 300 h. No residues of dust particles were found inside the filter pores in the metallographic investigations, which indicated that the filter grade was well suited for these conditions. Moreover, no corrosive products could be found on the surface and the cross-sectional investigation showed a close protecting oxide layer on top of the filter surface.

Figure 6. GKN's filter element that was used in the DFB gasification test campaigns.

Filter blinding studies

One of the main technical barriers related to high temperature filtration of biomass-derived gasification gas is filter blinding. In biomass gasification conditions, filters are traditionally operated in the temperature range of 350-550 °C as higher temperatures have reportedly induced filter blinding [2–6]. Since elevating the filter temperature to a level of 750-850 °C has been recognized as one of the key measures that could markedly improve the economics and efficiency of the process [7,8], the current target of filtration R&D at VTT is to find a solution that would allow filtration above 600 °C without blinding. Although the filter blinding mechanism is not yet fully understood, it has been associated with continued tar reactions on the filter - especially tar

polymerisation and soot/coke formation - that are enabled by the high temperature [2–5,8,9]. This in turn results in stickiness of the filter dust and consequently in poor detachment of the filter cake that is perceived as a continuous increase of baseline pressure drop across the filter.

Filter blinding was encountered in some of the DFB gasification test campaigns. According to VTT's earlier experience, a high content of heavy tars and low dust concentration in the gas combined with elevated filter temperatures are particularly favourable conditions for filter blinding [5,10]. In test campaign DFB 16/24, filter blinding took place in set points A and D where wood pellets were used as feedstock and the filter was operated at around 750 °C (Figure 7); the baseline pressure drop across the filter unit showed a constant increase in both set points. In the attempt to stabilise filter operation and inhibit further blinding, three different additives were tested and introduced to the raw gas stream (prior to the filter unit) in set point A: 1) cyclone dust (collected from the flue gas cyclone), 2) quartz sand, and 3) filter dust obtained from earlier gasification test campaigns. Quartz sand was used as an inert reference. The composition and properties of the additives are given in Table 2. The main operational parameters in DFB gasification test campaign 16/24 are summarised in Table 3.

As depicted in Figure 8, no inhibitive effect was observed when feeding cyclone dust or quartz sand, as the baseline pressure drop continued to increase with a fairly constant rate of 0.5 mbar/h. On the contrary, an instant response was obtained once additional filter dust was introduced to the gas (particulate concentration increased by 5.6%). The baseline pressure drop levelled off at around 40-41 mbar indicating that stable operation was achieved. The presence of char-containing filter dust clearly had a positive effect on the filter performance. Evidently, tars were adsorbed in the porous char on the filter surface, which prevented the formation of a sticky filter cake and the filter elements could be recovered.

Table 2. Composition and properties of the additives used.

Additive	Cyclone dust	Quartz sand	Filter dust
BET surface area, m ² /g	5.1	0.03	152
Density, kg/m ³	3.17	2.64	nd
Dry matter analysis	wt-%	wt-%	wt-%
C	3.9	-	50.2
H	0.1	-	0.7
N	< 0.1	-	0.3
S	nd	-	nd
O (as difference)	10	-	8.4
Ash	85.9	-	40.4

Figure 7. Filter performance in DFB test campaign 16/24 with wood pellets and bark as feedstocks. Testing of additives in set point A: 1 = cyclone dust, 2 = quartz sand, 3 = filter dust.

Figure 8. A close-up of set point A: filter performance and testing of additives (cyclone dust, quartz sand, filter dust).

Table 3. Main operational parameters in DFB gasification test campaign DFB 16/24. S+D = sand + dolomite

SET POINT	A	B	C	D
Feedstock	Wood	Bark	Bark	Wood
Bed material, wt/wt-%	S+D 30/70	S+D 30/70	S+D 30/70	S+D 30/70
Set point duration, h	22.5	12.5	6.0	12.3
GASIFICATION CONDITIONS				
Gasifier feed gases	steam / O ₂			
O ₂ in feed gases, vol-%	6.0	5.8	10.5	10.1
Feedstock, g/s	8.0	6.2	6.2	11.1
Steam, g/s	7.0	6.9	6.7	7.0
O ₂ , g/s	0.8	0.8	1.4	1.4
Bed material, g/s	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.9
Gasification temperature: bed/riser, °C	816 / 811	812 / 809	828 / 825	838 / 829
Gasification pressure: gasifier top, bar(a)	1.08	1.07	1.07	1.10
Steam-to-fuel feed ratio, kg/kg-daf	1.0	1.2	1.2	0.7
Fluidising velocity m/s	3.9	3.8	4.0	4.1
OXIDISER CONDITIONS				
Primary air, g/s	7.0	8.7	6.9	8.0
Bed material, g/s	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Oxidiser temperature: bed/freeboard, °C	881 / 863	884 / 864	873 / 862	882 / 867
Oxidiser pressure: oxidiser top, bar(a)	1.07	1.06	1.07	1.09
Fluidising velocity, m/s	0.26	0.33	0.25	0.29
GASIFICATION GAS COMPOSITION, vol-% (dry basis) ^a				
CO	13.4	11.4	11.1	15.4
CO ₂	25.7	26.4	29.5	27.4
H ₂	35.8	34.2	31.3	33.4
N ₂ (calculated as difference)	16.5	18.6	18.6	14.1
CH ₄	6.2	6.5	6.5	7.1
C ₂ H ₂	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.04
C ₂ H ₄	1.8	2.4	2.4	2.2
C ₂ H ₆	0.46	0.50	0.45	0.46
C ₃ -C ₅ hydrocarbons	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.02
H ₂ O measured, vol-% (wet basis)	41.9	45.4	45.3	39.6
Benzene concentration, g/m ³ n (in dry gas) ^b	10.7	13.5	13.9	13.1
Total tar concentration, g/m ³ n (in dry gas) ^b	7.8	12.7	12.5	10.7
Gasification gas flow rate, m ³ n/h (wet basis) ^c	73.4	63.3	64.2	88.4
FILTER CONDITIONS				
Filter temperature: inlet/outlet, °C	749 / 744	748 / 743	749 / 743	757 / 748
Face velocity, cm/s	3.1	2.7	2.7	3.7
Particulate concentration at filter inlet, g/m ³ n	15.3	7.0	4.7	12.4

^a Measured after the filter unit

^b Measured after the filter unit, including GC-unidentified compounds

^c Calculated value

Conclusions

The new sintered metal filter elements of GKN showed good filtration performance and high corrosion resistance in biomass gasification conditions. Filter blinding studies demonstrated that the presence of porous char on the filter surface plays a key role and filter dust recycling could be used to stabilize filter operation in high temperature conditions.

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Literature

- [1] H. Balzer, E. Mählig, A. Wierhake, Metal Filter Material Development for Hot Gas Filtration and Separation Applications, in: Present. 12th World Filtr. Congr. April 11-15, 2016. Taipei, Taiwan., n.d.
- [2] E. Kurkela, Formation and removal of biomass-derived contaminants in fluidised-bed gasification processes, in: VTT Publ. 287. VTT, Espoo, 1996: p. 47 + app. 87 p.
- [3] E. Kurkela, P. Ståhlberg, J. Laatikainen, M. Nieminen, Removal of particulates and alkali-metals from the product gas of a pressurized fluid-bed gasifier, in: Proc. Int. Filtr. Sep. Conf. Filtech Eur. 1991, Karlsruhe, Ger. 15–17 Oct., 1991.
- [4] E. Kurkela, P. Ståhlberg, J. Laatikainen, Pressurized fluidized-bed gasification experiments with wood, peat and coal at VTT in 1991-1992. Part 1. Test facilities and gasification experiments with sawdust, in: VTT Publ. 161. VTT, Espoo, 1993.
- [5] E. Kurkela, M. Kurkela, I. Hiltunen, The Effects of Wood Particle Size and Different Process Variables on the Performance of Steam-Oxygen Blown Circulating Fluidized-Bed Gasifier, *Environ. Prog. Sustain. Energy.* (n.d.).
- [6] E. Simeone, M. Nacken, W. Haag, S. Heidenreich, W. de Jong, Filtration performance at high temperatures and analysis of ceramic filter elements during biomass gasification, *Biomass and Bioenergy.* 35 (2011) S87–S104. doi:10.1016/j.biombioe.2011.04.036.
- [7] I. Hannula, E. Kurkela, A parametric modelling study for pressurised steam/O₂-blown fluidised-bed gasification of wood with catalytic reforming, *Biomass and Bioenergy.* 38 (2012) 58–67.
- [8] P. Simell, I. Hannula, S. Tuomi, M. Nieminen, E. Kurkela, I. Hiltunen, N. Kaisalo, J. Kihlman, Clean Syngas from Biomass - Process Development and Concept Assessment, *Biomass Convers. Biorefinery.* 4 (2014) 357–370.
- [9] A. Suokko, P. Simell, M. Nieminen, P. Luoma, T. Työppönen, J. Hannén, Simulation of hot gas filter blinding in laboratory conditions, in: 2009.
- [10] E. Kurkela, M. Kurkela, I. Hiltunen, Steam-oxygen gasification of forest residues

and bark followed by hot gas filtration and catalytic reforming of tars: Results of an extended time test, Fuel Process. Technol. 141 (2016) 148–158.